

The Aureus Under Trajan: The Metrological Evidence

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This article provides an in-depth examination of the metrological behaviour of Trajan's aureus issues (AD 98–117) and is based on the data of about 1800 coins, assembled in the course of a wider program of research on the coinage of Trajan's reign.

Trajan reduced the aureus weight from the standard of 1/43 pound, which had been used for the later issues of Domitian and under Nerva, to the Neronian standard of 1/45 pound soon after his accession, in AD 98/99, and this lower standard was adhered to throughout his reign. The reduction is to be interpreted in the context of Trajan's lowering of the silver content of the denarius alloy to c. 80 percent in AD 100.

Up to now, the metrology of Trajan's gold coinage (AD 98–117) has not received comprehensive treatment. This deficiency was recently pointed out by Cathy E. King: when discussing the problem of the weight standard of Trajan's half aureus in her long-awaited monograph on Roman *quinarii*, she did not have reliable figures for its double piece at hand (King 2007, 122). This lack of adequate metrological information on the Trajanic aureus is all the more unsatisfactory because we know for sure that there was a considerable reduction in the weight standard of the gold coinage under Trajan. The precise dating of the lowering, however, as well as

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its extent and whether it happened gradually or suddenly have been debated since the mid-nineteenth century.

The purpose of the present article is to supply much needed metrological data and to discuss briefly their implications in the context of the monetary economy of Trajan's reign. Metallurgical analyses of silver *denarii* recently conducted as part of the author's research on Trajan's coinage have brought about a fundamental change in the modern conception of this emperor's monetary reforms. As has been demonstrated (Woytek et al. 2007), the Roman mint had already reduced the silver content of the denarius alloy from slightly below c. 90 percent to c. 80 percent in the issues of AD 100. Thus, the reduction in fineness was much more marked and took place some years earlier than had been previously thought.¹ Therefore, it seems necessary to check how the metrology of Trajan's aureus fits with the evidence of his silver coinage.

The weight statistics presented in this paper are based on the material collected by the author since 2001, in the course of the preparation of a new corpus of the imperial coinage of Trajan, to be published shortly in the Viennese series *Moneta Imperii Romani* by the Austrian Academy of Sciences. For this book, information on more than forty thousand Trajanic coins has been gathered from the most important museum collections of the world—both published and unpublished—as well as from publications of the coin trade, auction catalogues, and dealers' lists. Among the technical data thus assembled, the weights of about 1,800 Trajanic *aurei* have been recorded, representing a most reliable sample size for our investigations.

The only Roman emperor of the late first century whose gold coinage has been studied in greater detail from the metrological point of view is Domitian (AD 81–96). Ian Carradice has calculated average weights for Domitianic *aurei* from the third and final period of this ruler's precious metal coinage, stretching from AD 85 to 96. One hundred and twenty-five *aurei* of this period in the Zemun hoard, discovered near Belgrade in 1875,² averaged 7.63 g (on contemporary weighings), whereas ninety-six pieces of the same period preserved in major museums' collections were found to average a little less, viz. 7.54 g (Carradice 1983, 50–51). This

1. According to the reconstruction of Walker (1977, 46, 55–57), which held sway for about three decades, Trajan reformed the denarius coinage only in AD 107, reducing the silver content just slightly, from c. 93 percent to between 88 and 90 percent. This hypothesis is based on fallacious figures obtained during analyses of Trajanic *denarii* with an entirely inappropriate analytical technique. See Butcher and Ponting (1998), 312, 322; Woytek et al. (2007).

2. See Ljubić (1876). This hoard, of which originally 230 *aurei* were acquired by the then National Museum Zagreb, is now partly dispersed, because duplicates were sold off in the late nineteenth century; the remaining eighty-five coins are today kept in the numismatic collection of the Archaeological Museum of Zagreb. I am extremely grateful to Ivan Mirnik for providing information on the hoard.

is not surprising, since the *aurei* in public collections come from various sources and inevitably have suffered different degrees of wear; the Zemun pieces, on the other hand, were part of a hoard closing early in Trajan's rule (AD 99) and are in excellent condition, because their circulating life was short. Carradice (1983, 51), therefore, regarded them as the "best guide to the weights of gold coins" in Domitian's reign.³

The aureus standard used in the final period of Domitian's gold coinage continued into the reign of his successor Nerva (AD 96–98), as can be seen from the frequency table below (Fig. 1). It shows the weight distribution of eighty-five *aurei* of Nerva; the data were assembled from the published collections of London, Paris, and Glasgow (Mattingly 1936; Giard 1998; Robertson 1962), as well as from specimens in trade recorded in the central card file (Numismatische Zentralkartei—NZK) at the Institute for Numismatics of Vienna University. It is the present writer's opinion that metrological analyses should preferably be carried out using frequency tables.⁴ The advantages of this tool were first described

Figure 1. Weights of eighty-five *aurei* of Nerva

3. It must be stressed, however, that the weights of the Zemun coins provided by Ljubić (1876) should be used with caution; comparison between the weights reported in his publication for some of the pieces that are still in Zagreb with these coins' weights as determined by modern balances shows that Ljubić's figures are systematically too high, by 0.01–0.03 g. Notwithstanding this, Carradice's contention is doubtless valid: a "corrected" average weight of the Zemun pieces would still be significantly higher than the average of the weights of Domitianic *aurei* from other sources.

4. It is still a point of debate whether mean weights (as calculated by Carradice), median, or

systematically by Hill (1924). In fact, apart from establishing the probable target weights, frequency tables give an impression of the metrological structure of ancient coin issues, and this information can be crucial.

The greatest concentration of aureus weights of Nerva falls between 7.55 and 7.59 g, although the range between 7.60 and 7.64 g is also well represented. It is probably here where the target weight is to be sought, and this target weight is in accordance with the data derived from the weights of Domitian's *aurei* in the Zemun gold hoard by Carradice (mean weight 7.63 g). As to determining the standard used by the Roman mint for the *aurei* in the last decade or so of Domitian's reign and under Nerva, the classic question of the weight of the Roman pound (*libra*) arises in as much as calculations range from 322.56 to 327.45 g.⁵ It is most difficult to find the correct equation, so that it has even been claimed that "an absolute figure seems unobtainable" (King 2007, 12). Recent research suggests that a value close to the highest of the cited figures (326.7 g) may be the correct one (Hahn 2005, 279–282; following Elsen 2004, 1–11). I have calculated a *libra* as c. 327 g, which leads to the calculation of a standard of forty-three to the pound for the *aurei* of Domitian and Nerva (theoretically c. 7.60 g, on this reckoning). Therefore, Domitian chose a standard considerably higher than Nero's reformed weight standard for *aurei*, which had been forty-five to the pound according to Pliny (*Naturalis Historia* 33.47), but much lower than the aureus standard of forty to the pound instituted by Julius Caesar, who introduced a regular Roman gold coinage in 46 BC.⁶

The *dies imperii* of Trajan was January 28, AD 98 (Hanslik 1965, 1045). When he ascended the throne, Trajan was not in Rome but rather in Germania Inferior, from where he went on a prolonged journey along the northern borders of the empire, returning to Rome only in the autumn of AD 99. Despite his absence, coinage was produced in Rome during this period. The first issue struck in the name of the new emperor by the Roman mint bears the legends IMP NERVA CAES TRAIAN AVG GERM P M (obv.) / TR P COS II P P (rev.), as was recognized by Strack (1931, 21–22).⁷ The peculiar sequence of names, "Imperator Nerva Caesar Traianus," suggests that the administration at Rome, without consulting the new ruler, devised the titulature. Indeed, this was put right—perhaps on

mode weights or frequency tables ought to be used in order to determine the "true" target weights of ancient coin issues. See, most recently, Butcher and Ponting (2005a, 110–111).

5. For the lower figure (calculated by L. Naville), see Duncan-Jones (1994, 213–215), finally opting for 322.8 g; for Boeckh's higher figure (advocated also by Mommsen), see Hulstsch (1882, 155–161).

6. This standard is mentioned by Pliny, too (*Naturalis Historia* 33.47); for Caesar's aureus standard, see Woytek (2003, 227, 264, 267; 2004, 344).

7. See also Wolters (1992, 284–289) on this point. Strack 1931, nos. 1–4 and 300–303.

Trajan's own order⁸—in the immediately following group of coins. The first issue was a very small one, struck probably only in the first two weeks or so of Trajan's rule (Wolters 1992, 288, n. 14). *Aurei* of this issue are excessively rare, with just five specimens in all being known to me. Weights are available for three of them: 7.31, 7.55, and 7.59 g, respectively.⁹ *Aurei* of the Roman Principate were not struck *al pezzo*, but *al marco*, so that individual weights could differ substantially. This explains the rather low weight of the piece in the British Museum, which does not affect the metrological interpretation of the issue as such: the first Trajanic *aurei* were certainly produced on the same standard that had been in use in the final phase of Domitian's reign and under Nerva, *viz.*, forty-three to the pound.

The first substantial issue of Trajanic precious metal bears the corrected legends IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM (obv.) / PONT MAX TR POT COS II (rev.) (Strack 1931, nos. 10–20). The absence of the title *pater patriae* (P P) is conspicuous, as compared to the issue at the very beginning of Trajan's reign. In fact, Pliny the Younger states in the *Panegyricus* (21.1–2) that Trajan repeatedly refused this honorific in the initial phase of his rule. Most likely, the administration of the Roman mint had automatically included the title in the legends of the first issue, because Trajan was expected to follow Nerva's example in accepting it at once (Strack 1931, 20, n. 46). The emperor, however, preferred to demonstrate his modesty and immediately ordered the removal of the “P P” from his titulature. In military diplomas dated February 20, AD 98, the title has already been dropped (*CIL* XVI, 42; Haalebos 1999, 208–209). After some months, the emperor finally yielded to the senate's insistence. The precise date of Trajan's assumption of the title is uncertain, but it has been inferred from another passage of the *Panegyricus* (57.1ff., esp. 5) that he assumed it shortly (?) before the consular election *comitia* for AD 99, perhaps before mid-October of 98 (Dierauer 1868, 42, n. 2; Strack 1931, 20–21).¹⁰ In this passage, Pliny mentions Trajan's refusal of the consulate for AD 99, adding praises of the emperor's modesty, although he had already been *Augustus et Caesar et pater patriae* at that time. The PONT MAX TR POT COS II issue lacking this title was therefore probably produced between February and the late autumn of AD 98, at the latest.

8. Wolters (1992, 288–289, n. 14), *contra* Seelentag (2004, 58–59). According to him, the change was ordered “von den stadtrömischen Vertrauten des neuen Herrschers.”

9. The pieces are (1) London, Mattingly 1936 (= *BMC*) Trajan 48; (2) Rome, Medagliere Capitolino, inv. no. 3530 (ex Campana coll.); and (3) Mazzini 1957, no. 591 (weight given as 7.50 g) = A. Hess AG, auction sale 5/4/1955 (“Goldmünzen und Goldmedaillen”), no. 85 (weight given as 7.60 g) = Numismatica Ars Classica AG auction sale 23 (19/3/2002), no. 1532 (weight given as 7.59 g).

10. On the dating of the consular elections/designations under the empire, see Mommsen (1887, 588), in the autumn “im October,” from Augustus on; and Strack (1931, 18, n. 40): “etwa Mitte Oktober.”

Figure 2. Weights of fifty-three *aurei* of Trajan, COS II (c. February–October?, AD 98). Mean weight: 7.48 g.

As can be seen (Fig. 2), a frequency table of aureus weights of this issue displays a distinct peak in the range from 7.55 to 7.59 g, just like the frequency table of *aurei* from Nerva's reign (Fig. 1). It seems clear that in the first nine months of Trajan's reign the weight standard of the gold coinage was not tampered with; it remained at forty-three to the pound.

The frequency table of aureus weights of the following issue, which again included the title P(ater) P(atriciae) and is to be dated in the period between c. mid-October 98 and the end of 99 (Strack 1931, nos. 21–28),¹¹ presents us with a different picture (Fig. 3). The metrological structure of this group differs fundamentally from the issues discussed up to now, because it covers a broad range of weights. Whereas nearly all the weights recorded for the *aurei* of Nerva and Trajan's first substantial issue cluster within 0.5 g, the present group covers nearly 1.0 g. There is no well-defined point of highest frequency for P M TR P COS II P P *aurei*, just an insignificant peak at 7.25–7.29 g within a concentration of weights in the broader range between 7.25 and 7.39 g. The table reveals a marked reduction of the weight standard.

11. Trajan became consul for the third time on January 1, AD 100.

Figure 3. Weights of sixty-one *aurei* of Trajan, COS II (c. October? AD 98–AD 99). Mean weight: 7.26 g.

Based on the weight of the *libra* adopted here, a lowering of the standard to $1/44$ pound would have resulted in a target weight of c. 7.43 g, whereas a standard of $1/45$ is equivalent to a theoretical target weight of c. 7.27 g. In our sample, the weight range between 7.40 and 7.44 g is represented by just a single specimen, while the peak—however insignificant it may be—is at 7.25–7.29 g, and twenty-six of the sixty-one weights recorded for this group are below 7.25 g. It seems very likely that the majority of the P M TR P COS II P P *aurei* were struck on the Neronian standard of forty-five to the pound. A glance at Figure 3 shows that a considerable number of specimens in the central range of weights (7.25–7.39 g) exceed this target weight, but this does not necessarily militate against our hypothesis.¹²

This issue could have represented a transitory phase, because not all of the *aurei* were struck on flans produced according to the new, lower standard. The broad range of weights covered by the issue and the unusual proportion of heavier

12. The presence of a considerable number of “overweight” *aurei* provisionally assigned to the standard of $1/45$ of a pound here seems explicable on our theory, since a new standard always tends to set in with rather heavy coins and is bound to decline later on. What is more, some of these coins might in fact be struck on “light” flans belonging to a higher standard. See below.

pieces can be explained by the use of (at least) two different standards by the mint of Rome in the months possibly between October 98 and the end of 99. The high weights (7.45–7.74 g) recorded for P M TR P COS II P P *aurei* (Fig. 3) are comparable to the weights of the first Trajanic issue and of Nerva's *aurei* struck on the standard of 1/43 pound. There are two possibilities: either the reduction of the standard was decreed before production of the new issue began and the mint, in the early stages of the coining process, merely used up heavier flans that had already been prepared, or the reduction was instituted while the minting of the group was already under way. Since using heavy flans at a time when the standard had already been lowered would have meant a considerable loss of revenue, the first possibility seems less likely. Probably the new target weight was introduced as the production of the issue was already in progress. The following *aurei* of this group with a weight of more than 7.50 g have been recorded:

Weight	Reverse Type	References	Location / Source
7.52 g	Germania seated l.	Strack 23; <i>RIC</i> 5	Utrecht, Schürmann coll., inv. no. 14, ex Ciani–Vinchon auction sale 6/5/1955, no. 328 (weight given as 7.53 g here)
7.52 g	Germania seated l.	Strack 23; <i>RIC</i> 5	Hess–Leu auction sale 27/3/1956, no. 381, ex Jameson coll.: Jameson 1980, no. 89 (weight given as 7.54 g here)
7.52 g	Germania seated l.	Strack 23; <i>RIC</i> 5	Paris, inv. no. Rothschild 244
7.56 g	Fortuna standing l.	Strack 22; <i>RIC</i> 4	Vienna, inv. no. 7869
7.57 g	Roma seated l.	Strack 25; <i>RIC</i> 8	Classical Numismatic Group auction sale 46 (24/6/1998), no. 1232, ex Dorotheum auction sale 975 (13/6/1955: Zeno coll., part 1), no. 597
7.62 g	Fortuna standing l.	Strack 22; <i>RIC</i> 4	cast in Madrid: Alfaro Asins 1993, Apendice, no. 155
7.68 g	Germania seated l.	Strack 23; <i>RIC</i> 5	Berlin, without inv. no.
7.73 g	Germania seated l.	Strack 23; <i>RIC</i> 5	Utrecht, general coll., ex J. Hirsch auction sale 24 (10/5/1909: Consul Weber part 2), no. 1331 (weight given as 7.71 g here) ¹³

Table 1. *Aurei* of Trajan, rev. P M TR P COS II P P: weight > 7.50 g.

13. This piece is probably to be identified with an aureus from the Zemun hoard, which is no longer at Zagreb. See Ljubić (1876, 28, no. 226), where the weight is given as 7.75g.

Table 1 needs some explanatory comments. Fortuna, Germania, and Roma are the only reverse types that are known for *aurei* of this issue; they had already been used in the PONT MAX TR POT COS II group. In the P MTR P COS II P P issue, they are all represented both among the heavy and the light pieces, with lighter pieces outnumbering the heavy ones by far. This shows that the reduction occurred early in the production of the issue. While the typological distribution of the coins does not give us a clue to the precise dating of the reduction of the standard, it indicates that *aurei* of all three types in this group were probably not struck sequentially, but more or less simultaneously.¹⁴ For all the aureus types, die links between very heavy specimens listed above and lighter specimens have been observed.¹⁵ That there was no typological differentiation between pre- and postreform *aurei* is in accordance with our expectations.

Trajan entered Rome for the first time as emperor probably in the autumn of AD 99 (Hanslik 1965, 1050–1051). Pliny the Younger records his presence in the capital at the *comitia* for the year 100, or about mid-October 99 (*Panegyricus* 63.1ff., 64.1ff.). He was elected consul for the third time at these elections, and entered office on January 1, AD 100 (Hanslik 1965, 1053–1054).¹⁶

14. It should, however, be noted that *aurei* with Germania are overrepresented among the heavyweight coins listed above. In general, pieces with this reverse are decidedly less common in the P MTR P COS II P P issue than Fortuna *aurei* and were probably produced on the same scale as *aurei* with Roma reverses, according to the figures available to me. In my files, there are thirty-nine Fortuna *aurei* of this issue and fifteen pieces each of the Germania and Roma types; unfortunately, for some of them no weights are available.

15. The Germania aureus in Berlin (7.68 g) was struck from the same pair of dies as BMC 34 (7.39 g), Paris, inv. no. AF 526 (7.32 g), and Giessener Münzhandlung auction sale 101 (6/3/2000), no. 782 (7.00 g). The Roma aureus from the Zeno coll. (7.57 g) was struck from the same obverse die as the Germania aureus ANS 1958.214.8 (7.42 g). The Fortuna aureus in Vienna (7.56 g) was struck from the same pair of dies as a Fortuna aureus in Glasgow, Robertson (1971), Trajan no. 14 (7.36 g).

16. As for Trajan's designation for the third consulship, Ehrhardt and Weiss (1995, 326) have put forward the hypothesis that it occurred only after the period November 6–12, 99, since an inscription with a letter of Trajan to the city of Delphi dating from this timespan styles the emperor simply COS II, without mentioning the designation. Though this interpretation is widely accepted today, the designation may simply have been left out in the inscription. Such an omission is perfectly plausible, as can be demonstrated by a numismatic analogy from Trajan's rule: the emperor's designation for the fifth consulship was not indicated on all the imperial issues produced in Rome after the consular election, but only on the bronzes, while the contemporary *aurei* and *denarii* (including the new cognomen DACICVS, which he assumed after December 10, 102) style Trajan only COS III (Strack 1931, nos. 55–60).

Figure 4. Weights of fifty-three *aurei* of Trajan, COS III (AD 100).
Mean weight: 7.21 g.

The *aurei* produced by the Roman mint in AD 100 were struck according to the Neronian standard of forty-five to the pound (target weight: 7.27 g), as can be seen in Figure 4. The diagram exhibits a “classic” distribution, with the greatest concentration of weights to be observed in the range between 7.25 and 7.29 g; the next higher weight group is markedly less well represented. In this issue, the weight range covered by the recorded specimens is again just about 0.5 g, far smaller than that in the preceding P MTR P COS II P P group. This third issue, comparable in the number of samples to the first two issues, was struck on a single weight standard.

This standard was employed in the issues of Trajan’s fourth consulate, too (Fig. 5), which covered two years. The sample size for these coins is considerably larger than that of the preceding groups. The weight peak in the frequency table falls somewhat lower than that of the COS III issue, in the range of 7.20–7.24 g, but the next higher class is also well documented. Clearly the same target weight (7.27 g on our reckoning) as in the preceding issue was intended, but it was achieved with less accuracy in this group.

The issues of the second, third, and fourth consulates cover the first five years of Trajan’s reign (AD 98–102) and are generally taken to constitute the first of the three major phases of his coinage. Before examining the development of the Trajanic aureus during the emperor’s fifth and sixth consulates (AD 103–111 and 112–117, respectively), we should compare the results obtained so far with previous research on the topic.

Figure 5. Weights of 139 *aurei* of Trajan, COS IIII (AD 101–102).

Mean weight: 7.16 g.

The metrological information on Trajanic gold coins provided by Mattingly and Sydenham (1926, 242) in the first edition of volume 2 of the standard handbook *The Roman Imperial Coinage (RIC)* is misleading. Without mentioning a change in standards the authors state: “In gold, the aureus and *quinarius* . . . were issued at the reformed Neronian weight.” Bolin, in his influential monograph, also failed to make a clear distinction between heavyweight and lightweight Trajanic *aurei*.¹⁷ While Strack (1931, 12) did not deal with the weight standard of Trajan’s gold coins at all, Mattingly (1936, xiv) briefly surveyed the problem: “The aureus of the heavier standard, as struck by Domitian through almost all his reign, continued over Nerva into the first year of Trajan: it then fell again to the reduced standard of Nero.”¹⁸ West appears not to have been entirely convinced of the correctness of this statement,¹⁹ but Mattingly was, in fact, not too far off the mark,

17. The standard for *aurei* introduced by Nero was temporarily abandoned by Domitian and Nerva, but it was reintroduced by Trajan (Bolin 1958, 191).

18. See also the table of weights provided (Mattingly 1936, xv), with the comment: “The ‘early’ class is of Trajan’s first year only”; Mattingly correctly states that *aurei* of the “heavy” standard occur both in Trajan’s PONT MAX TR POT COS II and in the P M TR P COS II P P issue. He gives the average weight of the two classes as being 7.59 and 7.22 g respectively, adding that a frequency table for the lighter Trajanic *aurei* “shows a peak at . . . 7.19” (xv, n. 2).

19. “It seems probable that early in his reign Trajan reduced the weight of the aureus to the

with one important caveat: one cannot be sure about the absolute dating of Trajan's reduction, as outlined above. Since production of the P M TR P COS II P P issue, in which the metrological change is to be observed, may have started as late as 99, credit once more has to go to Theodor Mommsen. In his *Geschichte des römischen Münzwesens*, working from an exiguous amount of data, Mommsen surmised that the weight standard of Domitian's *aurei* continued not only into the first but possibly into the first two years of Trajan's reign.²⁰ Mommsen thus prudently left open the possibility that heavy *aurei* were still struck in AD 99.

In recent years, scholarly discussion of the metrology of Trajan's aureus has shifted to the special problem of the character of the lowering of its weight. Wolters has repeatedly argued that there was no abrupt change in gold standards, as Mattingly had postulated, but rather a gradual reduction in the period from AD 98 to 101.²¹ King, while accepting that Trajan lowered the aureus weight fairly early in his reign, was rather cautious about Wolters' particular theory. Her reluctance to adopt it was due to the impression that the sample sizes investigated by Wolters were too small to allow far-reaching conclusions.²² In fact, the concept of a gradual reduction of the aureus standard under Trajan over such a long timespan probably cannot stand. While the issue of AD 98 conforms to Domitian's and Nerva's standard of forty-three to the pound, the issue of AD 100 (COS III) doubtless utilizes the restored Neronian standard of forty-five to the pound, with the metrological differences between the COS III and the subsequent COS IIII issues being minimal. It is true that the intermediate P M TR P COS II P P group represents a transitional stage, but careful analysis has shown that it was struck partly on the old and partly on the new standard.

reformed standard of Nero, but unfortunately the weights of the . . . coins assigned to A.D. 98/99 give no clear point of concentration" (West 1941, 77).

20. "Fühlbar steigt das Gewicht wieder namentlich unter Domitian, dessen Goldstücke selbst im Durchschnitt um 0.2 bis 0.3 Gr. über 1/45 Pfund stehen. Diese reelle Prägung erstreckt sich auch noch auf Nervas Regierung und die ersten zwei Jahre Traians; späterhin hat dieser Kaiser . . . etwa wie Nero gemünzt" (Mommsen 1860, 754). Paribeni cited Mommsen on this matter: "sembra che l'aureo che pesava in media grammi 7,40 sotto i Flavi scenda con Traiano a 7,20" (Paribeni 1926–1927, 2:176–177).

21. "eine allmähliche Reduzierung des Goldgewichts, keine Reform, die diese Maßnahme auf einen Schlag durchführte" (Wolters 1992, 297); "A gradual reduction . . . can be deduced from this—not a reform . . . in one step" (Wolters 1993, 280); "stufenweise[n] Gewichtsreduktion, die . . . erst im Jahr 101 . . . abgeschlossen war" (Wolters 1999a, 118).

22. "The date under Trajan when the standard on which gold was minted reverted to that of Nero has been the subject of some discussion, although there is no doubt that it took place early in the reign. Wolters suggested in a recent study that the reduction was gradual rather than occurring in a single stage. . . . Unfortunately, the sample size of all of his groups is very small. . . . While his theory may be correct, the available evidence is not sufficient to prove it" (King 2007, 122).

Figure 6. Weights of 196 *aurei* of Trajan, COS V (c. AD 103–107). Mean weight: 7.16g.

Figure 7. Weights of 357 *aurei* of Trajan, COS V (AD 107–111). Mean weight: 7.16g.

The mint continued to use the Neronian gold standard reintroduced by Trajan before his third consulate throughout the rest of his reign. Figures 6 and 7 show the weight distributions of Trajanic *aurei* of the two main groups of the COS V period. Both are very large, especially the second one, and both bear legends in the dative case—a typical feature of Trajan's later issues, which is to be observed from late AD 103: IMP TRAIANO AVG GER DAC P M TR P COS V P P (obv.) / SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI (rev.),²³ and IMP TRAIANO AVG GER DAC P M TR P (obv.) / COS V PP SPQR OPTIMO PRINC (rev.).²⁴ As was recognized by Mattingly (1936, lx) and Hill (1970, 36, 139), these two groups were minted consecutively, with the change in legends probably falling in the year of Trajan's second Dacian triumph, AD 107.

Both frequency tables show peaks in the weight range of 7.20–7.24 g, exactly like the *aurei* of the fourth consulate (cf. Fig. 5). The weight distribution of the later group is extremely regular, doubtless due to the large sample size (nearly 360 pieces). The same is true of the first group of COS VI *aurei*,²⁵ minted before Trajan assumed the title “Optimus” in August AD 114 (Fig. 8). Here the sample is even bigger, nearly 370 pieces, and the distribution is once more very regular; in all these three cases the weight peaks in the range of 7.20–7.24 g clearly support the hypothesis that the intended target weight was 1/45 of a pound. It may be noted that the early COS VI *aurei* were struck rather heavier than the immediately preceding group, as can be deduced from the excellent representation of pieces of the next higher weight range after the peak, viz. 7.25–7.29 g.

This trend continued in the period from summer 114 to February 116, that is, between the senate's vote to add “Optimus” to Trajan's titlature, following the annexation of Armenia, and the emperor's assumption of the title “Parthicus” after his initial successes against the Parthians (see Hanslik 1965, 1097, 1100). The weight peak of *aurei* of this timespan²⁶ (Fig. 9) is at 7.25–7.29 g, thus marginally higher than in the foregoing groups. The standard of forty-five to the pound was maintained, although the emperor had been at war since October 27, AD 113.²⁷ The remarkable percentage of *aurei* in the weight range 7.15–7.19 g may perhaps be taken to prefigure a metrological development apparent in Figure 10.

23. For gold and silver of this group, see Strack (1931, nos. 78–113).

24. Strack (1931, nos. 121–163 [gold and silver]).

25. For the precious-metal coins of this group, see Strack (1931, nos. 171–179, 184–197, 202–217a).

26. They belong to two different classes. See Strack (1931, nos. 218–226, 227–240).

27. On the date of his *profectio* for the east, see the discussion by Hanslik (1965, 1094) (with references).

Figure 8. Weights of 368 *aurei* of Trajan, COS VI (AD 112–114). Mean weight: 7.15 g

Figure 9. Weights of 297 *aurei* of Trajan, COS VI, Optimus (AD 114–116). Mean weight: 7.18 g.

Figure 10. Weights of 224 *aurei* of Trajan, COS VI, Parthicus (AD 116–117).
Mean weight: 7.17 g.

The frequency table of *aurei* from the final phase of Trajan's rule (Fig. 10) might prompt speculation whether, in the end, the armed conflict was to have repercussions for the weight of the gold coins: In any case, a slight shift downward in weight may be observed for the "Parthicus" coins,²⁸ the peak in the diagram being only at 7.15–7.19 g. This was not anything like the adoption of a new standard for *aurei*, to be sure—a lowering to 1/46 of a pound would have corresponded to a target weight of 7.11 g, and the metrological structure of the group makes it clear that we are far from that. But it shows that the official standard of forty-five to the pound was achieved with less precision at the end of Trajan's rule than in the preceding groups. The late Trajanic *aurei* tend to be somewhat lighter as a group, although this point should not be pressed. Even so, the evidence suggests that Trajan's heavy fiscal expenditures on his Parthian War might have led to a minimal adjustment of the aureus weight.

A survey of the metrology of Trajan's gold coinage shows that this emperor opted for a return to Nero's aureus standard of forty-five to the pound very early in his reign—even before his entry into Rome, at a time when he was still on an inspection tour of the northern borders of the empire. The shift from the heavier standard of Domitian and Nerva to the lighter was conducted during the minting of the second substantial aureus issue of Trajan's rule bearing the reverse legend

28. Strack (1931) nos. 241–260 (gold and silver).

P M TR P COS II P P, between autumn 98 and the end of 99. From this point on, the Neronian standard was employed—with minor variations—for all of Trajan's aureus issues, while the fineness of the gold coinage was left untouched.²⁹

Taken together with the results of metallurgical analyses of Trajanic silver coins performed recently, this evidence indicates that Trajan modelled his monetary policy in regard to the precious metal coinages completely on Nero's. While the decision to switch to Nero's light aureus weight was made in the first or second year of his rule, Trajan's other measure, the reduction in the silver fineness of the *denarii* to the Neronian level, is to be dated to AD 100. All the Trajanic *denarii* of the second consulship (AD 98–99) analyzed with modern methods were found to have been produced on a standard of c. 87 percent silver, on average,³⁰ whereas the *denarii* struck from his third consulship on contain just c. 80 percent silver. This is exactly the standard created by Nero in AD 64 and used for the majority of his post reform *denarii*, as well as under Vespasian (Butcher and Ponting 2005b, 179; 1998, 312, 321).

Trajan thus reformed the precious-metal coinages in two steps: he reduced the weight of the more valuable gold coins first, and a few months later, in the year of his third consulship, he debased the alloy of the silver coins. What were the motives for his reforms? West (1941, 80) was sceptical on this point: "The reasons that led Trajan to return to the Neronian standard for gold and silver are no more clear than the reasons that led Domitian to attempt a return to the standards of the pre-Neronian period." In the meantime, the background of the changes under Domitian has been studied in detail by Carradice (1983, 163), who convincingly held that "Domitian's monetary reform of 82 can be seen as part of a much wider policy to restore former standards of morals and order." Indeed, the rare efforts to improve the quality of the coinage during the Principate can best be understood in the context of restorative political concepts,³¹ while reductions in standard often are to be put down to fiscal stress. Domitian's debasement in AD 85, for example, was probably a consequence of the huge army pay increase of 84 and should also be seen in connection with further military campaigns to be conducted by Domitian in the years 85 to 87: "There can be no doubt that this was an economic necessity" (Carradice 1983, 162).

29. Trajanic *aurei* average c. 99 percent, just like the gold coins of his predecessors; for metallurgical analyses, see Callu et al. (1985, 82–83), Blet-Lemarquand (2006, 168–169).

30. Twenty-one *denarii* of Trajan's second consulship analyzed by Butcher and Ponting (1998, 312, 322) were found to have a fineness between 84.3 and 91.8 percent; eight *denarii* of this period analyzed in Vienna (Woytek et al. 2007) were found to contain between 85.3 and 94.0 percent.

31. This view is shared by Wolters (1999b), 405.

I propose to view Trajan's reduction of precious-metal standards early in his reign in this perspective, too. It seems that this emperor, practically from the outset of his reign, was taking measures to relieve the state's budget by cutting expenses in the production of coinage. For a ruler who had no moral objections to this strategy, it was a straightforward choice. Nero had demonstrated successfully that it was simply of no use to invest more precious metal in this sector than necessary, and the weight and fineness standards set by Nero had proved to be high enough to maintain a functioning monetary economy; Trajan was happy to follow his example. As for the precise reasons that induced him to pursue a policy of economizing from the beginning of his rule, different suggestions may be made.

Bennett (1997, 127–128), in a recent biography of Trajan that met with a lot of criticism,³² ventured a short-term explanation: the debasement was carried out in view of the extraordinary expenditure due soon after Trajan's accession, *viz.* the donative for the troops and the *congiarium* to be paid to the citizens of Rome—as is well known, spending pressures at the start of a new reign were typically very high.³³ Evidence on Trajan's payments in this period comes from three different sources, two texts and a coin type: Pliny (*Panegyricus* 25.2) records *datumque congiarium populo, et datum totum, cum donativi partem milites accepissent* (“the *congiarium* given to the people, paid out in full, while the soldiers had received just a part of their *donativum*”). He heaps praises on Trajan, his *liberalitas*, and especially his equal treatment of the people of Rome and the soldiers—quite a paradox, given the fact that the latter had reportedly received in cash just a part of the sum due: *aequati sunt . . . populo milites eo quod partem, sed priores, populus militibus quod posterior, sed totum statim accepit*.³⁴ Both payments (first the donative, later the *congiarium*) had been made long before the day when the *Panegyricus* was delivered, on September 1, AD 100 (on the date of publication, see Woytek 2006). *Sestertii* of Trajan depicting the scene of the distribution of the *congiarium* in the

32. See, e. g., Seelentag (2004, 16, n. 10) (with reference to a review by W. Eck).

33. On this point, see Harl (1996, 221–222), Duncan-Jones (1994, 238–239), and Wolters (1999b, 247–248). On *congiaria* in general, see van Berchem (1939).

34. “The soldiers were equated with the people in that they were paid first, but only in part, the people with the soldiers in that they were paid second, but received the full sum at once” (*Panegyricus* 25.2). Seelentag (2004, 180–182) misinterprets the passage to the effect that Trajan had paid already two donatives to the soldiers at the time when the *Panegyricus* was drafted, in AD 100. Wolters (1999a, 124, n. 29) draws attention to the fact that, according to Vegetius (*Epitoma Rei Militaris* 2.20), customarily only one half of donatives was paid out in cash, while the second half was kept in the troop's chest (or, more precisely, was transferred to the soldiers' accounts): *Illud vero ab antiquis divinitus institutum est, ut ex donativo, quod milites consecuntur, dimidia pars sequestraretur apud signa et ibidem ipsis militibus servaretur, ne per luxum aut inanium rerum comparationem ab contubernaliibus posset absumi*. According to Wolters, Trajan may therefore have followed the normal practice.

emperor's presence and bearing the date COS II³⁵ give us the clue to a closer dating of this event. It must have taken place after the ruler's return to Rome in the autumn of 99, but before his designation for the third consulship, which probably occurred in October or November of the same year.

There is no precise indication in the sources as to when the donative to the army was paid, although a date immediately after the accession is generally assumed (Seelentag 2004, 180, n. 2). Nor do we know the amount of the donative,³⁶ while the Chronographer of the year 354 records the figure of 650 *denarii* for Trajan's *congiarium/-a*.³⁷ Since the emperor distributed two further *congiaria* after his two Dacian triumphs, in 103 and 107,³⁸ this remarkable sum may represent an addition of all three gifts,³⁹ although the reliability of the source has been challenged even on this assumption (Duncan-Jones 1994, 249). Domitian had distributed three *congiaria* of only seventy-five *denarii* each, as Suetonius and the Chronographer record,⁴⁰ and Nerva had given this typical amount once, as the latter source notes. Unfortunately, we must conclude that there is little hard evidence for Trajan's spending on the donative and *congiarium* at the beginning of his reign, and the total sums involved—indeed, even the individual amounts—remain more or less unknown.

Nevertheless, it is quite clear that the accession donative for the legions must have been granted during the first year of Trajan's reign, in AD 98, which he spent entirely on the Rhine and Danube. It is implausible that the new emperor would have taken the risk of delaying the payday unduly. Most probably, the donative will therefore have been paid out in a period to which the PONT MAX TR POT COS II issue belongs—in other words, at a time when the aureus standard had not yet been lowered. The *congiarium* of autumn 99, on the other hand, was in all likelihood distributed in freshly minted P M TR P COS II P P *aurei* of the restored Neronian standard of forty-five to the pound.

35. Strack (1931, no. 323). Legends: IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM P M TR P (obv.) / COS II P P CONG(iarium) P(opulo) R(omano) (rev.).

36. For comparative figures, see Duncan-Jones (1994, 257).

37. Chronographus anni CCCLIII p. 146 Mommsen (Monumenta Germaniae Historica, Auctores Antiquissimi IX/1): *Traianus cong. dedit X DCL*.

38. Both are recorded on *sestertii*. See Strack (1931, nos. 356 [CONGIAR SECVND; AD 103], 415 [CONGIARIVM TERTIVM; AD 107]).

39. Syme (1930, 59) first examined the possibility that the figure represents a single *congiarium*—perhaps the payment of AD 99—before he took it to be an addition of three, still “a monstrous total.” Paribeni (1926–1927, 1:268) thought that the *congiarium* of AD 103 alone amounted to 650 *denarii*.

40. Suetonius, Domitianus 4.5; his statement is confirmed by a precise indication of the Chronographer: *congiarium dedit ter X LXXXV*. On Domitian's *congiaria*, see Rogers (1984, 63).

That the government was able to economize on bullion by paying out the *congiarium* of AD 99 in lighter *aurei* will have been a most welcome collateral effect of the monetary reform, but it would not have been its primary goal, as Bennett thought. This may be deduced, *inter alia*, from the fact that the lowering of the aureus standard was not an isolated incident but was accompanied by a debasement of the denarius in the following year,⁴¹ when both *congiarium* and *donativum* had long been distributed. Evidently, this reform was not planned as a short-term measure. Trajan's debasement rather has to be interpreted under the aspect of the long-range political and military program of the emperor at the outset of his reign. It is pretty clear that Trajan planned to conquer Dacia from his accession; the costly preparations of the war would have begun immediately, and the emperor may have decided to return to Nero's lower precious-metal standards mainly in order to finance his aggressive foreign policy.

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41. This must not be interpreted merely as a measure to adjust the relation between gold and silver coins once the weight standard of the gold had been reduced (see also Wolters 1993, 275). Changes in one metal did not necessarily entail alterations to the other, as may be seen, e.g., from Nero's last denarius issue produced on a 90 percent standard, while the weight of the aureus was left unchanged (Butcher and Ponting 2005b, 179–180).

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